

The Oxyfluorfen Exhibits Estrogenic Action Induced Change on the Hypothalamic-Pituitary-Gonadal-Adrenal Axis and Impairment in Fertility in Mice *Mus musculus*

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Abstract:

Background: Oxyfluorfen is one of the herbicides placed in the third category of toxicity used to control broad-leaf and grassy weeds. The investigation aims to evaluate the effect of Oxyfluorfen on adult male mice.

Objectives: The present investigation studied one of the Herbicides - Oxyfluorfen impact (an endocrine disruptor) on the hypothalamic-pituitary-gonadal-adrenal axis, infertility and AChE activities in male adult mice.

Methods: The treatment group received 350mg/kg, 500mg/kg and 750mg/kg body weight for 14 days and autopsied on the 15th day of the experiment. The serum was collected and subjected to ELISA using specific antibodies for sex steroids. The testis and adrenal were subjected to histology. The results revealed significantly decreased fertility index, serum testosterone level, sperm motility and count with increased morphological abnormalities in sperm and an insignificant increase in estradiol level in males. Histological observations of the testicle revealed degenerative changes of seminiferous tubules, reduced interstitial space and Sertoli cell disruption could signify the impact on fertility. The hypertrophy of adrenal medullary cells and decreased AChE activity indicate neuroendocrine imbalance.

Conclusion: The observed results reveal that Oxyfluorfen exhibits estrogenic action, induced changes on the hypothalamic-pituitary-gonadal-adrenal axis and impairment in fertility, and hence may be considered as an endocrine disruptor.

Keywords: Oxyfluorfen, Histopathology, Infertility, AChE activity.

Key Points: Herbicidal effects, Sperm abnormality, Sperm count, Hormonal assay.

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Introduction

The present scenario depicts that, the use of pesticides has drastically increased in the environment. A pesticide is any substance or mixture of substances intended for preventing, destroying, repelling or mitigating any insects, rodents, nematodes, fungi, weeds or any other form of life declared to be a pest and any substance or mixture of substances intended for use as a plant regulator defoliant and desiccant [1].

Pesticides have contributed to the improvement of our food supply and quality of our environment by controlling harmful pests and insects [1]. However many pesticides can be expected to reach non-target organisms. Herbicides commonly known as weed killers constitute the major class of pesticides and they account for 48% of total pesticides [2]

Herbicides have widely variable toxicity and act as endocrine disruptive compounds [3] They comprise several structurally diverse classes of chemicals, each with its distinct mode of action and use patterns. Selective herbicides kill specific targets while leaving the desired crop relatively unharmed. Some of these act by interfering with the growth of the weed and are often synthetic mimics of natural plant hormones.

Herbicides cause, cell disruption, carcinogenic impacts, negative fertility effects, and neurological impacts [4]. Several herbicides have been reported to have endocrine-disrupting effects on vertebrates, interfering with steroidogenesis and sex determination [5, 6]. Oxyfluorfen is a pre-emergent and post-emergent broadleaf and grassy weed

herbicide. It is one among them and is said to disrupt the endocrine system. It causes irritant effects to the eyes, skin and occasionally respiratory problems. It is a potent **protoporphyrinogen oxidase inhibitor**, a membrane-bound enzyme involved in the heme and chlorophyll biosynthesis pathway. They exert their phototoxic activity on weeds by preventing chlorophyll formation. Mild liver and renal toxicity also occurred [7].

The present study is designed to assess the toxicity of Oxyfluorfen on the male reproductive system, on the morphological changes in the testis, sperm concentration, abnormality and motility of sperm and alteration of AChE activity in brain after intra-peritoneal injection in Swiss albino mice.

In the past three decades, there has been a decrease in sperm concentration throughout the industrialized world [8]. The sperm count (no. of sperm/ml) has dropped precipitously throughout much of Europe and America. In addition, the number of normal sperm fell from 60 million/ml to 20 million/ml in the same period. Scientists have suggested that testicular dysgenesis syndrome may be largely due to endocrine disruptors [9]. In the present day, one would expect not only females but also males to have reproductive problems and those do. Male reproductive endpoints from animals and humans were reported [10].

In male reproductive system, it has been suggested that exposure to EDCs may result in impaired sperm motility, concentration, volume, and morphology, as well as increased sperm DNA damage [11]. Endocrine disruptors like pesticides and herbicides cause infertility in males [12]. Stress induce alterations in various physiological responses even leading to a pathological state. The studies on central neurotransmitter mechanisms in stress have mainly been of biogenic amines. The central cholinergic system has not been adequately explored for its involvement in stress despite its key role in the regulation of several central functions [13].

The effect of pesticides alters the negative feedback regulation of the hypothalamus, resulting in an uncontrolled release of ACTH and corticosterone from the pituitary and adrenal cortex, respectively. An alteration of any of the regulatory inputs such as a change in the brain neurotransmitter levels or a disruption of the feedback response would alter corticotropin-releasing factor (CRF) release from the hypothalamus and impair pituitary and adrenal functions, stress response, behavior and immunity [14]. Acetylcholine is a major neurotransmitter in Alzheimer's disease. We **aim** to examine this neurotransmitter by measuring the activity of Acetylcholinesterase in the brain. Synthesis and termination of Ach activity are regulated by choline

acetyltransferase (ChAT) and Acetylcholinesterase (AChE), respectively. Pesticides act as inhibitors of the enzyme acetylcholinesterase (AChE) [15], which degrades acetylcholine (ACh), which acts as a neurotransmitter in the central nervous system (CNS) of insects, rodents, and humans [15]. Disruption of the cholinergic system with a decline in the activity of AChE is a common feature of neurodegenerative processes such as Alzheimer's disease. Because Ach is the main neurotransmitter in the cortex and this structure is directly involved with the thalamocortical pathway, we believe it is important to study the cholinergic pathway. Mice have been selected for the present study as they have physiological systems and responses similar to those of men. Also, they have remarkable genetic similarities to humans [16].

Materials and Methods

Experimental Animals: Healthy adult male Swiss albino mice weighing about 30 to 37 grams were obtained from the Mice colony, Department of Zoology, Karnatak University, Dharwad. They were kept in polypropylene cages (290×220×140 mm) with stainless steel grill tops and bedded with paddy husk and maintained at a temperature of 28 ± 2°C at 50–60% humidity, and a 12 h light-dark cycle for at least a week before the experiment. They were maintained under standard housing conditions with free access to a standard diet and water ad libitum during the experiment. The experimental protocol was followed as approved by CPCSEA guidelines for the care and use of small laboratory animals.

The animals weighing approximately 30 to 34 gms were randomly divided into four experimental groups and administered with Oxyfluorfen. Each group consisting of five mice (n=5), one acted as a control and the remaining received Oxyfluorfen treatments as follows: Group 1 - 350 mg/kg (0.3ml) body weight; Group 2 - 500 mg/kg body (0.4ml) body weight; Group 3 - 750 mg/kg body (0.5ml) respectively. The animals were handled with gloved hands. They were restrained by grabbing them over the shoulders and turned over so that the abdomen was exposed during administration, at 9.30 am for 14 days. The drug was injected intraperitoneally in the lower right or left quadrant of the abdomen. Oxyfluorfen drug (2-chloro-1-(3-ethoxy-4-nitrophenoxy)-4-(trifluoromethyl) of 5 ml is dissolved in 50 ml of distilled water (stock solution). The body weights of the animals were recorded throughout the experimental period starting from Day 1. By the end of the 2nd week, the mice were sacrificed 24 hours after the last treatment followed by overnight fasting. The mice were administered with light ether anesthesia under sterile conditions. Testes were dissected, trimmed connective tissues, washed using normal saline to eliminate blood contamination, and dried with

blotting filter paper. They were excised and kept in Bouin's fixative for histopathological assessment.

The semen from the Epididymis was collected by chopping the Epididymis into pieces and incubating in a Phosphate Buffer pH 7.4 for the analysis of sperm count, sperm motility, and sperm abnormality. The brains of the male mice were dissected and collected. They were stored at -80°C in the deep freezer and later the AChE activity was analyzed.

Histopathological Assessment: Testis was examined for histopathological changes under a light microscope. The testes were fixed in Bouin's fixative, embedded in paraffin wax before sectioning at $5\mu\text{m}$ thickness and stained with hematoxylin and eosin.

Sperm Count: The epididymis was chopped into pieces and incubated for 10 minutes at 37°C in 3 ml pre-warmed Phosphate Buffer pH 7.4. The sperms were released in the solution. 0.5 ml of the solution was diluted in 9.5 ml of Sperm Diluting Solution [5 gm of NaHCO_3 , 1 ml of 35 % Formalin and 25 mg Eosin per 100 ml distilled water]. $10\mu\text{l}$ of sperm suspension was charged on Neubauer's Chamber for counting of sperms. The sperms were counted in the RBC chamber.

Sperm Count = Total no. Of sperms in 5 chambers X 50,000 X 100 sperms /ml.

Sperm Motility: The semen from epididymis was taken in the pre-warmed phosphate buffer and a drop of it was taken on a slide to analyze sperm motility every 15 sec up to 1 min [17].

Sperm Abnormality: The semen from the epididymis was collected in the 2 ml of normal saline and a drop of it was smeared on a slide and stained with eosin. It was observed under a microscope in four different areas and the abnormalities were recorded [18].

AChE Activity: $200\mu\text{l}$ Phosphate Buffer + $100\mu\text{l}$ of Acetylthiocholine iodide + $40\mu\text{l}$ of Sample incubate for 30 min at room temperature. After incubation terminate the reaction by adding 1.8 ml of DTNB reagent. The optical density for each sample was measured by spectrometry at 412 nm.

Biochemical Assays: A blood sample was withdrawn through the jugular vein and collected into a plain tube. The samples were allowed to clot, and centrifuged and the serum samples were sent for analysis using a standard automated technique in a Diagnostic Laboratory according to the procedures described by the manufacturers. Blood samples were collected and serum was obtained from control and treated animals after 2 weeks of treatment, for biochemical studies.

Enzyme-linked immunosorbent Assay (ELISA) for plasma testosterone and $17\text{-}\beta$ estradiol

Plasma collection for the assay: Mice were killed by decapitation on the last experimental day. Blood was collected into EDTA-coated tubes (150 mg EDTA/L in 9g NaCl/L) and plasma was prepared by centrifugation.

Plasma T and E2 levels in the male mice were measured by competitive binding immune enzymatic determination (ELISA) using antibodies specific for each chromosome according to the protocol supplied with respective kits (Equipor Diagnostics, Saronno, Italy). Horseradish peroxides (HRP) were used, as an enzyme-labeled antigen that competes with the sample antigen. HRP binds to a limited number of anti- $17\text{-}\beta$ estradiol (antibody) and anti-testosterone (antibody) sites on a microplate (solid phase) E2 and T were assayed in duplicate.

Later E2 and T concentrations in the sample were calculated based on the series of standards from S0 to S5 for testosterone and S0 to S5 for estradiol. The color intensity was inversely proportional to the concentration of hormones E2 and T in the sample. The hormone concentration was compared with the standard curve (Epoch ELISA reader, Biotech, USA). The absorbents of the standard and the samples were monitored against the blank at 450 nm from both E2 and T mean absorbance and relative percentage (B/B0%) were calculated and interpolated. The value of the standards was expressed as B/B0% on the standard curve to obtain the corresponding value of the concentrations as ng/ml in T and pg/ml in E2.

Statistical Analysis: We employed the following statistical tools to analyze our data systematically. Data were expressed as $\text{MEAN}\pm\text{SE}$. The level of statistical significance was set at $p<0.05$ and $p<0.01$. Comparison of normally distributed variables among groups were made using SPSS and the values are recorded in tables.

Results

Body weight: The body weight of the control mice was recorded daily, and it shows a variation of 2-3 grams daily due to the consumption of the food. The average body weight of the control mice is 37.5 ± 2.43 .

The body weight of the oxyfluorfen-treated mice was also recorded daily. It revealed a certain decrease in the body weight from the day of the experiment to the day of the autopsy 29.5 ± 3.42 . This drug has affected the physiology, endocrine system, and reproductive system of the male mice to some extent. Due to hormonal regulation, the body weight has altered (Table 1).

Testis weight: The weight of the testis is 0.2612 ± 0.000047 mg. The weight of testis was reduced in the treated mice compared to the control group 0.2431 ± 0.000851 mg. (Table 2)

Histological Analysis

T.S. of Testis: The testis of control mice shows an ovoid body with a functional unit seminiferous tubule. They are held together by connective tissue. The seminiferous tubules are lined by germinal epithelium. The seminiferous tubules consist of primary spermatocytes, secondary spermatocytes, spermatids, and spermatozoa. The connective tissue consists of specialized cells called Leydig cells or interstitial cells. These are clusters of cells with a central nucleus and prominent nucleoli. (Fig. 1 and 2)

The number of primary spermatocytes, secondary spermatocytes, spermatids, and spermatozoa is reduced. An increased vacuolization seen between the seminiferous tubules and also in the lumen. The number of Leydig cells decreased. There was a spermatogonial arrest and debris formation in the testis. (Fig. 1 and 2)

T.S. of adrenal: This gland is a compound structure consisting of an outer cortex and inner medulla. The hormone of the cortex is steroids, whereas those of the medulla are amines. The location of the medulla and cortex is very clear structurally as well as functionally. The medulla is central and surrounded by cortex tissue. The cortex is again divided into three layers. They are outer zona glomerulosa, middle zona fasciculata, and inner zona reticularis. The medulla has distinctly clumped chromaffin cell groups. (Fig. 3)

Histopathological examination of sections from mice adrenals treated with oxyfluorfen showed mild lesions throughout the cortical regions of Zona glomerulosa and Zona reticularis and changes in the medullary region.

Most of the sinusoids in the zona glomerulosa and zona reticularis of the adrenal cortex were filled with red blood cells; it is an indicative sign of congestion. Red blood cells were seen as a dense collection in most of the blood vessels (vascularization) in the medulla. There was an increase in the size of chromaffin cells. (Fig. 3)

Sperm Dynamics

Sperm count:

Control mice: The sperm were seen to be normal in count in the control mice. The count differs from the environment, the food we supply, and its behavior. The counts were taken in millions/mL. The normal sperm count was 160 ± 4.18 million/ml.

Treated mice: In the treated mice, the sperm count was observed to decrease in number to 45 ± 2.73 million/mL, as the doses increased when compared to the control mice ($F_{3,16}=213.24$, $p=0.000$; Table 3).

Sperm motility

Control mice: The rapid, free, and progressive motility of the sperm was observed in the control mice; for every 100 sperm, 27.94 ± 2.18 were motile.

Treated mice: The sperm were less motile compared to the control (16.70 ± 2.6). The sperm were non-progressive motile or sluggish and immotile (dormant) sperms, which decreased in fertilizing capacity. The significant difference is ($F_{3,16}=213.24$, $p<0.05$; Table 4).

Sperm abnormality

Control mice: A normal sperm is formed of head and tail regions. The base of the head (the point of attachment with the tail region) is thicker than the diameter of the tail, and the head tip is sharply bent into a hook shape. The sperm aberrations were very low or not seen in the control mice.

Treated mice: The sperm aberration was high in the treated mice; as the dose increased, the abnormality of the sperm was also increased. The treated mice showed many abnormal sperm characterized by a coiled tail, amorphous head, looping midpiece, bent neck, and headless. The significant difference is $p<0.05$ (Table 5).

Acetylcholinesterase activity: In the treated mice, the AChE activity decreased as the doses increased, enhancing the cholinergic activity by raising the ACh level, i.e., inhibition of metabolism in the adult male mice. (Table. 6)

Hormonal assays (E2 and T): The alterations in T blood serum level were noticed in the treated group significantly at ($p<0.05$), and there is no significant difference in E2 blood serum level. (Table 7).

Table 1: Showing average body weight of control and treated mice in gms

Control		Group 1		Group 2		Group 3	
Initial	Final	Initial	Final	Initial	Final	Initial	Final
37.5±2.43	37.5±1.19	31.5±1.16	29.5±2.13	35.75±2.38	31.75±2.18	32.0±3.80	29.25±1.80

Table 2: Showing the weight of testis in control and treated mice in mg.

	Control	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3
Testis weight in mg	0.2612±0.000047	0.2503±0.000082	0.2402±0.0729	0.2431±0.000851

Table 3: Effect of Oxyfluorfen on sperm count (millions/ml) in control and treated mice.

Sperm Count In Millions/MI	Control	Group1	Group2	Group3	F And P Value
Readings	160.0±4.18	118.00±1.22	70.0±4.74	45.00±2.73	$F_{3,16}=213.24$ $p=0.000$

n = 4-1, values are expressed in MEAN±SE

Table 4: Effect of Oxyfluorfen on sperm motility/100 sperms in control and treated mice

Sperm Motility/100	Control	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	F and P Value
Readings	27.94±2.18	23.21±1.32	17.966±4.17	16.70±2.16	$F_{3,16}=3.71$ $P= 0.034$

n=4-1, values are expressed in MEAN±SE

Table 5: Effect of Oxyfluorfen on sperm abnormality/100 sperms in control and treated mice

Sperm Abnormality	Control	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	F and P Value
Bent Neck	10.25±1.97	41.75±5.93	93.50±2.10	82.75±25.26	$F_{3,12}=8.627$ $P= 0.003$
Coiled Tail	28.25±1.65	41.25±4.49	43.75±2.25	49.50±3.79	$F_{3,12}=7.37$ $P= 0.005$
Amorphous/Oval Head	6±0.707	6.25±2.21	13±2.19	24±7.34	$F_{3,12}=4.43$ $P= 0.026$
Looping Mid piece	25±2.12	43.5±1.44	47.75±12.3	76±17.62	$F_{3,12}=3.79$ $P=0.040$
Head Less	6.25±1.25	18.75±5.43	17.75±0.25	59±33.37	$F_{3,12}=1.86$ $P=0.190$

n= 4-1, the values are expressed in MEAN±SE

Table 6: Effect of Oxyfluorfen on AChE activity in control and treated mice

Concentration μ /mol	Control	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	F and p value
Readings	0.8950±0.05795	0.8750±0.0741	0.8875±0.07087	0.8800±0.06745	$F_{3,12}=0.017$ $p=0.997$

n= 4-1, values are expressed in MEAN±SE

Table 7: Effect of Oxyfluorfen on testosterone and estradiol levels in control and treated mice.

Control	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	F and p value
0.7643±0.0544	0.5402±0.04478	0.5402±0.0075	0.3565±0.0526	$F_{3,12}=14.299$, $p=0.000$
0.3473±0.176	0.2957±0.16	0.4688±0.148	0.435±0.118	$F_{3,12}=0.267$, $p>0.05$

FIGURE-01

FIGURE-02

Figure 1: the testis of control mice shows ovoid body with functional unit seminiferous tubules whereas in treatment group the testis shows dystrophy somniferous tubules

Figure 2: The number of primary spermatocytes, secondary spermatocytes, Spermatids and spermatozoa are reduced, increased vacuolization, number of Leydig cells decreased spermatogonial arrest and debris formation in the testis, treatment group I, II, III respectively. (H&E satin x 400)

FIGURE-03

Figure 3: Control- Medulla and cortex are very much clear, medulla is central and surrounded by cortex tissue. Treated - mild lesions throughout the cortical regions of Zona glomerulosa and Zona reticularis, dense collection of red blood cells and blood vessels (vascularisation) present in the medulla. There was an increase in the size of chromaffin cells. (H&E stain x 400)

FIGURE-04

Figure 4: Control group showing the normal sperm shape, and treatment groups showing abnormalities like coiled tail, bent neck, amorphous /oval head, headless, looping midpiece.

Discussion

Oxyfluorfen is a toxic chemical widely used as a herbicide to kill broad leafy weeds. There are a few

studies available to evaluate the adverse effects of extensive use of herbicides. Herbicides like Atrazine [19], Paraquat [20] etc; are already approved as endocrine disruptors. The endocrine

system is sensitive to disturbing influences that can severely impair the whole development of the organisms. Several naturally occurring and synthetic chemicals have been shown to exert these adverse effects upon the endocrine system across animal classes including mammals [21]. Organophosphorus pesticides such as Malathion, Dichlorous and Chlorpyrifos have been reported to affect the male reproductive system of adult rodents inducing histopathological alterations in testes, spermatogenic disturbances as well as altered testosterone levels [22, 23, 24].

In this study, we tried to summarize the effects of the herbicide Oxyfluorfen that altered the male reproductive system, and adrenal gland and analyzed AChE activity in mice. Pesticide-herbicides, insecticides and fungicides were reported to impair fertility suggesting spermatogenesis, a decrease in sperm count, sperm motility and sperm abnormality. Insecticides not only decrease sperm count but also reduce sperm motility. Male rats receiving Carbendazim revealed decreased testicular weight, altered sperm morphology, testicular atrophy and thus infertility [25]. The herbicide Endosulfan exposure causes a decline in the testosterone levels in mice which causes improper spermatogenesis due to degeneration of seminiferous tubule. Spermatids were also degenerated which causes azoospermic conditions leading to infertility in mice [26]. In our histological studies, testis revealed that seminiferous tubules were adversely affected and atrophy of Leydig cells was observed. Similarly, rarefactions of Leydig cells in pesticide diamethoate treated rats were observed [27]. Control group showed well-organized seminiferous tubules with distinct primary, and secondary spermatocytes and Spermatids were normal. Seminiferous tubule degeneration, sloughing, atrophy and degeneration of germ cells and partial arrest of spermatogenesis in pesticide received rats [28], in the present study we observed malformed Spermatids, clustered cells of seminiferous tubules with fragmented walls and degenerated seminiferous tubules which caused the accumulation of debris. There was distant space between each seminiferous tubule, vacuolization was observed in the seminiferous tubules and there was a decrease in the number of Leydig cells. These results reciprocate chlorpyrifos effect in rats [29]. Sperm count represents the amount of cells available to perform reproductive function. In both experimental animals and humans, fertility is dependent not only on having adequate numbers of sperm but also on the degree to which those sperm are normal [30]. The sperm counts of treated rats with Ethanol extract of *C. aphylla* were greatly varied from the control mice and the sperm count decreased in a dose-dependent manner. The caudal epididymal sperm exhibited rapid progressive

motility in the control; meanwhile, the motility in the rat treated with ethanolic extract of *C. aphylla* showed a decrease in motility as the dose increased and this property is dose-dependent [31]. Any negative impact on the motility would seriously affect fertilizing ability [17]. Similar results were observed in our study as doses increased, sperm count and sperm motility decreased in the treated mice when compared to those of control mice.

The sperm morphology significantly decreased in the immunized animals throughout the experiment and the effects were more prominent. Morphological studies denote that more than 70% of the sperms were abnormal in shape characterized by pin head, large head, tapering head, oval head, small head, headless, double head, bent neck, looped midpiece, coiled tail and double-tailed sperms. In (GnRH-BSA) immunized animals of all groups. The abnormal sperm results in less fertilizing capacity and genetic variation [17, 18]. Similar results were found in our studies, there were significant changes in the morphology of sperm when compared to control sperm, and the percentage of abnormal sperm in the treated group variedly increased. The sperm abnormalities were studied in five types Headless, Bent neck, Coiled tail, looping midpiece and oval/amorphous head.

DZN exposure caused a reduction in the Leydig cells [32]. The decreased number of Leydig cells could be the cause of testosterone shortage, which disrupts testosterone biosynthesis and spermatogenic deficiency [33,34,35]. Our results demonstrated that the number of Leydig cells in the treated mice decreased meanwhile we observed a decrease in Testosterone levels. Testosterone helps to maintain spermatogenesis in an almost quantitative fashion in rats [30]. Testicular Leydig cells play a critical role in male reproductive function, alteration in the Leydig cells could be due to many different pathological or experimental situations associated with spermatogenesis deficiency. [35, 36, 37].

In Oxyfluorfen-treated male mice, we observed an increase in the size of chromaffin cells and an enlargement of blood capillaries (vascularization). Similar results were also reported by [38]. Cytoplasm vacuolations in certain zones of adrenal glands (Zona fasciculata and Zona reticularis) and the sinusoids filled with erythrocytes are observed (Zona reticularis and Zona glomerulosa). Our observations are in agreement with previous findings [20]. The catecholamine is inhibitory to pancreatic β cells (insulin). Probably the compound might have a hyperglycemic condition. This herbicide compound has induced stress in the mice which may lead to in heart rate. Epinephrine increases both the force and rate of heartbeat by stimulating the cardiac muscles β -ARs (adrenoreceptors). The hypertrophy of chromaffin

cells may affect the regulation and maintenance of the nervous system. It is reported that Oxyfluorfen in the diet decreases adrenal weight and some histopathological changes [39]. The space formation and hypertrophy of chromaffin cells were also observed by [40].

AChE is an enzyme essential for the normal functioning of the central and peripheral nervous system and is widely distributed in the neural and non-neural tissues. Acetylcholinesterase is one of the hydrolytic enzymes that modulate the amount of neurotransmitter substance acetylcholine at neuron junctions. AChE activity in the liver completely varied in the treatment group and found to decrease the components [41]. Exposure to pesticides could result in a clinical or sub-clinical disruption of the cholinergic pathways potentially contributing to neurodegenerative diseases later in life. Diseases like Parkinson's, Alzheimer's or Lewy body disease. Exposure to pesticides during early life may result in a higher susceptibility to subsequent environmental exposures, potentially unmasking silent neurotoxicity later in life [1].

The inhibitory potency of glyphosate against acetylcholinesterase was observed in the brain, liver and kidney in rats [42]. It is expected that decreased AChE may enhance cholinergic activity by raising Ach levels (inhibition of metabolism), thereby maintaining/improving cognitive functions [43].

In the present study, the Acetylcholinesterase enzyme activity which is responsible for acetylcholine degradation was significantly decreased in adult mice. Hence there was inhibition in the AChE activity in the brain and affected the cholinergic pathway.

Conclusion

- Herbicide Oxyfluorfen altered the histoarchitecture of the testis (like reduced Leydig cells, distantly placed seminiferous tubules) and adrenal gland.
- Oxyfluorfen impairs the male reproductive system by altering total sperm count, sperm motility, and sperm abnormality.
- Due to the decreased AChE activity the cholinergic pathway altered.
- E2 and T levels decreased in the blood serum.

In conclusion, in this work, Oxyfluorfen shows a toxic effect and may be considered as an endocrine disrupting chemical since it affects the testis and adrenal. However, further investigations are needed.

References

1. Aguilar C. Pesticides and pesticide combinations on brain neurochemistry: Doctoral dissertation, Virginia Tech. 2004.

2. Gupta P K. Chapter 24 - Herbicides and fungicide. Biomarkers in Toxicology 2014; 409-431.
3. Pogrmic-Majkic K, Fa S, Dakic V, Kaisarevic S, Kovacevic R. Upregulation of peripubertal rat Leydig cell steroidogenesis following 24 h in vitro and in vivo exposure to atrazine. Toxicological Sciences 2010; 118(1):52-60.
4. Ghazi RM, Nik Yusoff NR, Abdul Halim NS, Abdul Wahab IR, Ab Latif N, Hasmoni SH. Health effects of herbicides and its current removal strategies. Bioengineered 2023; 14(1): 2259526.
5. Marlatt VL, Lo BP, Ornostay A, Hogan NS, Kennedy CJ, Elphick JR, Martyniuk CJ. The effects of the urea-based herbicide linuron on reproductive endpoints in the fathead minnow (*Pimephales promelas*) Comp Biochem Physiol C Toxicol Pharmacol 2013 ;157(1):24-32
6. Wilson VS, Lambright CR, Furr JR, Howdeshell KL, Earl Gray Jr.L. The herbicide linuron reduces testosterone production from the fetal rat testis during both in utero and in vitro exposures Toxicology Letters 2009;186(2):73-77.
7. Overview of Oxyfluorfen Risk Assessment, 2002.
8. Carlsen E, Giwercman A, Keiding N, Skakkebaek NE. Evidence for decreasing quality of semen during past 50 years. British medical journal 1992; 305(6854): 609-613.
9. Scott.F. Gilbert 9thEd
10. Working PK. Male reproductive toxicology: comparison of the human to animal models. Environ Health Perspect 1988; 77:37-44.
11. Henriques, MC, Loureiro, S, Fardilha, M, Herdeiro, MT, Henriques, MC, Loureiro, S, et al. The role of endocrine-disrupting Chemicals in Male Fertility Decline. Male reproductive health. London: IntechOpen (2019).
12. Sharma A, Mollier J, Brocklesby RWK, Caves C, Jayasena CN, Minahas S. Endocrine-disrupting chemicals and male reproductive health. Reprod Med Biol 2020;19(3):243-253
13. Das A, Rai D, Dikshit M, Palit G, Nath C. Effect of unpredictable stress on cognition and brain acetylcholinesterase activity in adult and aged mice. Indian journal of pharmacology 2002; 34(6):416-421.
14. Singh AK. Acute effects of acephate and methamidophos and interleukin-1 on corticotropin-releasing factor (CRF) synthesis in and release from the hypothalamus in vitro. Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology Part C: Toxicology & Pharmacology 2002; 132(1): 9-24.

15. Mladenović M, Arsić BB, Stanković N, Mihović N, Ragno R, Regan A, Milićević JS, Trtić-Petrović TM, Micić R. The Targeted Pesticides as Acetylcholinesterase Inhibitors: Comprehensive Cross-Organism Molecular Modelling Studies Performed to Anticipate the Pharmacology of Harmfulness to Humans In Vitro. *Molecules* 2018;23(9):2192
16. Aguilar C. Pesticides and pesticide combinations on brain neurochemistry: Doctoral dissertation, Virginia Tech. 2004.
17. Eissa FI, Makawy AI, Badr MI, Elhamalawy OH. Assessment of 3, 4- dichloroaniline toxicity as environmental pollutant in male mice. *European Journal of Biological Sciences*. 2012; 4(3): 73-82.
18. Ganaie JA, Shrivastava VK. The effect of active immunization with gonadotropin releasing hormone conjugate (GnRH-BSA) on gonadosomatic indices (GSI) and sperm parameters in mice. *Iranian Journal of Reproductive Medicine*, 2008; 6 (3): 119-123.
19. Pogrmic-Majkic K, Fa S, Dakic V, Kaisarevic S, Kovacevic R. Upregulation of peripubertal rat Leydig cell steroidogenesis following 24 h in vitro and in vivo exposure to atrazine. *Toxicological Sciences* 2010; 118(1):52-60.
20. Chohan MS, Tahir M, Lone K, Jafari F, Sami W, Khan, TM. Paraquat-induced toxicity in adrenals in albino mice. *American Journal of Biomedical Sciences* 2011; 3(3): 228-235.
21. Hrouzková S, Matisová E, Andraščíková M, Horváth M, Húšková R, Ďurčanská J. Survey of low-level endocrine disrupting pesticides in food matrices in Slovakia 2012. *International Journal of Environmental Analytical Chemistry*, 92;(13):1546-1562
22. Choudhary N, Goyal R, Joshi SC. Effect of Malathion on reproductive system of male rats. *Journal of environmental biology* 2008; 29(2):259.
23. Farag AT, El-Aswad AF, Shaaban NA. Assessment of reproductive toxicity of orally administered technical dimethoate in male mice. *Reproductive toxicology* 2007; 23(2): 232-238.
24. Huang LG, Lin P, Gong CY, Zhang J, Zhou Q, Gong XD, Zeng L. Pathological changes in the testes of the rats with hypospadias induced by dichlorvos. *National journal of andrology* 2006; 12 (8): 693-5.
25. L Earl Gray Jr, Joseph O, Ralph L, Jerome G, Georgia R, Ralph C. Carbendazim-induced alterations of reproductive development and function in the rat and hamster. 1990. *Fundam Appl Toxicol* 15(2): 281-297.
26. Singh JK, Nath A, Kumar A, Md Ali M, Kumar R. Study on the effect of endosulfan on testosterone level and seminiferous tubule of testis of mice. *World J Envir Poll* 2011; 1: 1-4.
27. Uzun FG, Kalender S, Durak D, et al. Malathion-induced testicular toxicity in male rats and the protective effect of vitamins C and E. *Food Chem Toxicol*. 2009; 47:1903–1908.
28. Ferdinand N, Pierre W, Augustave K, et al. Effect of Dimethoate (an organophosphate insecticide) on the reproductive system and fertility of adult male rat. *Am J Pharmacol Toxicol*. 2014; 9:75–83.
29. Babazadeh M Najafi G. Effect of chlorpyrifos on sperm characteristics and testicular tissue changes in adult male rats. *Vet Res Forum* 2017; 8(4):319–326.
30. Toxicology excellence for risk assessment. 2005
31. Revathi P, Vani B, Sarathchandiran I, Kadalmani B, Shyam KP, Palnivel K. Reproductive toxicity of Capparis aphylla (Roth.) in male albino rats. *Int J Pharm Biomed Res* 2010; 1(3): 102-112.
32. Fattahi E, Parivar K, Joursaraei S, Moghadamnia AA. The effects of diazinon on testosterone, FSH and LH levels and testicular tissue in mice. *Iranian Journal of Reproductive Medicine* 2009; 7: 59-64
33. Maxwell LB, Dutta HM. Diazinon-induced endocrine disruption in bluegill sunfish, *Lepomis macrochirus*. *Ecotoxicology and environmental safety* 2005; 60(1): 21-27.
34. Hussein HK, Elnaggar MH, Al-Zahrani NK. Antioxidant role of folic acid against reproductive toxicity of cyhalothrin in male mice. *Global Adv Res J Environ Sci Toxicol* 2012; 1(4): 066-071.
35. Omotoso G, Onanuga I, Ibrahim R. Histological effects of permethrin insecticide on the testis of adult wistar rats. *Ibnosina Journal of Medicine and Biomedical Sciences* 2014; 6(03): 125-129.
36. Dufau ML, Cigorruga S. Androgen Biosynthesis in Leydig Cells after Testicular Desensitization by Luteinizing Hormone-Releasing hormone and Human Chorionic Gonadotropin. *Endocrinology* 1979; 105 (6):1314-1321.
37. Walsh LP, McCormick C, Martin C, Stocco, DM. Roundup inhibits steroidogenesis by disrupting steroidogenic acute regulatory (StAR) protein expression. *Environmental health perspectives* 2000; 108(8): 769-776.
38. De Falco M, Sciarrillo R, Capaldo A, Russo T, Gay F, Valiante S, Laforgia V. The effects of the fungicide methyl thiophanate on adrenal gland morphophysiology of the lizard, *Podarcis sicula*. *Archives of environmental contamination and toxicology* 2007; 53: 241-248.

39. Oxyfluorfen - Human Health and Ecological Risk Assessment 2005.
40. Hashin KA, Sreedevi amma KK, Santosh, Shoba SV. Study on the influence of Benzene hexachloride hexachloro cyclohexane in certain endocrine glands of Gerbil. Proceeding of the World Congress on Engineering. 2009.
41. Sai Sundeep Y, Hanchinalmath JV, Lakshman Kumar D, Shivasharanappa K, Kiran. B. In Vitro Evaluation of effect of Thyroxin on Protein, Total ATPase and Acetyl Cholinesterase activities in kidney and liver tissue of Albino rat. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research 2014; 3(8):697-704.
42. Larsen KE, Adrián LL, Lifschitz, Lanusse CE, Virkel GL The herbicide glyphosate is a weak inhibitor of acetylcholinesterase in rats. Environmental Toxicology and Pharmacology 2016; 45:41-44.
43. Papandreou MA, Dimakopoulou A, Linardaki ZI, Cordopatis P, Klimis-Zacas D, Margarity M, Lamari FN. Effect of a polyphenol-rich wild blueberry extract on cognitive performance of mice, brain antioxidant markers and acetylcholinesterase activity. Behavioural brain research 2009; 198(2): 352-358.